

Supplementary Material

1 Updated analysis of the trench 2 data

We present the trench 2 exposed in Baize et al. (2015) with a new analysis of the sediment dates and offsets documented in this paper. The OxCal website tools are used to calculate the calibrated ages. We newly compute them in order to derive an updated chronological framework of the paleoearthquake events. The initial trench interpretation defines the same sequence of events from the most recent to the oldest (note that we inverted the numeration compared to Baize et al. (2015)).

E1 is an unconformity surface marked by a limited vertical throw (max. ~70 cm) on the westernmost rupture strand (F3) and an opening on F2; like in 2015, we suspect that this event is historic, and most probably due to the 1797 Riobamba M7.5+ earthquake with its close epicenter (Beauval et al., 2010). E2 to E4 represent events, with either a well-defined stratigraphic signature (base of clastic layer, unconformity) or marking fault terminations.

Following this geological interpretation of the deposits and their arrangement, we defined in Oxcal a chronological framework (*'Sequence'*) following Lienkaemper and Ramsey (2009) recommendations (figure S2). According to geological section interpretation, radiocarbon samples (*'R_Date'*) from the same soil unit were grouped into a single *'Phase'* that we separated one from each other by *'Boundaries'* representing potential discontinuities in sediment record. We then define the stratigraphic location of *'Events'*, i.e. paleo-earthquakes, and of the historic earthquake (*'C_Date'*).

Figure S1: Geological section of trench T2 dug in 2009 in Rumipamba (Baize et al., 2015). We simplified the drawing in representing in a same caption the bedrock fragment-rich horizons (colluvial wedges), the soil units, and the bedrock, as well as the fault planes and surrounding shattered rocks. We underline the stratigraphic location of the event horizons that are used in the OxCal analysis.

Figure S2: Snapshot of the OxCal chronological model (note that the scheme is not presented in the stratigraphic order), defined to reproduce the observations in trench 2. Reported 14C dates ('R_Date') do not account for their 'sign', i.e. before or after our era. The 'Phases' represent homogenous soil layers, grouping samples in a similar stratigraphic position. 'Boundaries' are separations between 'Phases', with potential sedimentation gaps. 'C_Date' was introduced to show up the 1797 Riobamba earthquake which is thought to have ruptured the surface in the trench.

Name	Unmodelled (BC/AD)			Modelled (BC/AD)			Indices				Select	Page break			
	from	to	%	from	to	%	A _{model} =101	A _{overall} =100.9	A _{comb}	A			L	P	C
▼ Sequence														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary Start 1				-8835	-6580	95.4							96	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/>
▼ Phase 1														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F3	-6767	-6593	95.4	-6761	-6591	95.4			100.7				99.7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F2	-5617	-5487	95.4	-5617	-5489	95.4			99.7				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary End 1				-5600	-4020	95.4							99.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/>
E4				-5277	-3741	95.4							99.2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary Start 2				-4610	-3657	95.4							99.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/>
▼ Phase 2														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 10	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F5	-2874	-2621	95.4	-2875	-2631	95.4			100.4				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 11	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F4	-3645	-3521	95.4	-3646	-3521	95.4			99				99.6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 12	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F0	-3706	-3634	95.4	-3706	-3633	95.4			99.7				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 13	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F11	-3766	-3647	95.4	-3762	-3646	95.4			102.8				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 14	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F1	-2905	-2696	95.5	-2906	-2697	95.4			102				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 15	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary End 2				-2856	-1994	95.4							99.6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 16	<input type="checkbox"/>
E3				-2722	-1621	95.4							99.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 17	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary Start 3				-2525	-1427	95.4							99.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 18	<input type="checkbox"/>
▼ Phase 3														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 19	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F10	-361	-168	95.4	-361	-171	95.4			101.8				99.7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 20	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-feu	-1506	-1402	95.4	-1506	-1400	95.4			99.3				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 21	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary End 3				-338	692	95.4							99.4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 22	<input type="checkbox"/>
E2				-163	875	95.4							99.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 23	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary Start 4				70	973	95.4							99.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 24	<input type="checkbox"/>
▼ Phase 4														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 25	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date T2-F7	777	986	95.3	776	985	95.4			97.6				99.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 26	<input type="checkbox"/>
Boundary End 4				787	1666	95.4							99	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 27	<input type="checkbox"/>
C_Date EQ Riobamba	1796	1797	95.4	1796	1797	95.4			100				100	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Page														<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure S3: OxCal Output table with the modelled dates for the 14C samples and for the ‘events’ introduced in the chronological model exposed in figure S2. Ages are in a 2σ bracket.

Figure S4: Example of a 95.4% probability density function for the date of the T2-F2 sample, determined based on the Radiocarbon age and corrected thanks to the IntCal13 calibration curve (snapshot from the OxCal software output file).

Figure S5: Example of a 95.4% probability density function for the date of the E4 event defined between ‘Phase1’ and ‘Phase2’ based on stratigraphic and geometrical arrangement. The date of the event is determined based on the Radiocarbon ages of samples in these two layers and corrected thanks to the IntCal13 calibration curve (snapshot from the OxCal software output file).

2 Catalogues of geological evidences

With this supplementary material, we associate a free access repository which gathers an extensive set of observations and pictures that were made during a series of 5 in 2009, 2010, 2014, 2015 and 2016 field campaigns, and a series of strip maps. All this information is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3706207>

From the various field observations and 4m-spatial resolution DEM analysis, we could propose a map of geomorphological features (*Line_DEM.shp in StripMaps.zip*) which, correlated with fault outcrops, is reported in the five strip maps and location map (*Supplementary Figures S6 to S11 in StripMaps.zip*). On those maps, we report the position of the field waypoints which are referenced in the *Obs_Waypoints_2009-to-2016.xlsx in Photos.zip*, with a short description. We also provide a collection of the most relevant sites' pictures to illustrate the landscapes, outcrops and features that reveal the active tectonics of the Central Ecuador area between Rumipamba and Pisayambo. These pictures are stored in the *Photos.zip* folder.

Photos.zip

- A series of 87 pictures and annotated images
- *Obs_Waypoints_2009-to-2016_new.xlsx*

StripMaps.zip

With a series of maps located on Figure S6_Strip_Map_General.png, from south to north:

- Figure S7_Strip_Map_1.png
- Figure S8_Strip_Map_2.png
- Figure S9_Strip_Map_3.png
- Figure S10_Strip_Map_4.png
- Figure S11_Strip_Map_5.png

On those maps, one can locate the sites described in *Obs_Waypoints_2009-to-2016_new.xlsx* (some of them depicted on pictures in *Photos.zip*). Fault lines are available in *Line_DEM.shp*.